

**ПЕДАГОГИК ВА
ПСИХОЛОГИК
ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР**

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1-СОН

**PEDAGOGICAL AND
PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES**

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A DIFFERENT APPROACH FOR LANGUAGE LEARNING PROFILES AND TEACHING PHILOSOPHY STATEMENT

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ANNOTASIYA: Ushbu maqolada til o'rganish uslubi, tajribasi va temperamenti turlicha bo'lgan ikki xil o'rganuvchilarga psixologik-pedagogik yondashgan holda turlicha o'qitish metodikasini nazariy tahlil qilish va uning amalda qo'llanilishi yoritib berilgan. Shuningdek, sohadagi yetuk olimlarning bu mavzuga oid fikr-mulohazalarini o'rganish bilan birga o'qitishga oid shaxsiy pedagogik falsafa qarashlari aks etgan.

Kalit so'zlar: CLT, CBI, TBI, TPR, suggestopedia, GTM, ESL, IP, SLA, Krashenning gipotezasi, L1, L2.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В этой статье освещается теоретический анализ различных методов обучения и его практическое применение с психолого-педагогическим подходом к двум типам учащихся с разным стилем изучения языка, опытом и темпераментом, а также изучение мнений по этому вопросу, отражены личные педагогические мировоззренческие взгляды на преподавание.

Ключевые слова: CLT, CBI, TBI, TPR, суггестопедия, GTM, ESL, IP, SLA, гипотеза Крашена, L1, L2.

Currently, I am working at Lyceum and I conduct sophomore students. In the beginning of the course, I chose and started observing the two language learners whose names are Asya and Guli and their age is 17. Although both of them are the same years old, that is, teenage learners, their prior language instruction, learning strategies, personalities and identities are different. Currently, their level is about intermediate and they have their own approaches towards language learning process. Both Asya and Guli have developed their learning techniques owing to their language experience and exposure throughout years.

Section 1: Detailed learner profiles

Student 1, Asya

Her first language is Russian and she has acquired the language subconsciously in a language environment at home but she can also speak Uzbek outside. When it comes to the English language, she had no previous formal instruction. Nevertheless, she lives in her relative's house in the city because of her study and the family members are English teachers. Therefore, in two years, she had the opportunity to learn the language in a communicative way based on interaction with her relatives as well as watching English movies and getting feedback.

That is why, she acquired the language due to her much immersion. She is kind of gregarious and eager to interact with others. Therefore, she has developed his speaking and listening skill. Even though she does not have a deeper understanding of grammar such as modal verb, adverbs, transitive verbs and participle, she can speak English and comprehend the teacher's speech during the lesson.

Student 2, Guli

Her first language is Uzbek and she studies in Uzbek group at Lyceum. Notwithstanding, she knows Russian to some extent. She has been learning English for 2-3 years at a learning center. She is introvert by nature and she is unwilling to participate during my English lessons. She has a perfect command of English grammar, reading and writing. She can create texts and essays based on conscious morphological structure in an accurate way and achieve the best results from tests. She has learned the language very well, by focusing on only grammar and vocabulary books. Because she has a visual learning style, she prefers to learn grammar and new words by writing a lot. However, she has had no exposure to a spoken environment outside the classroom. Therefore, she cannot express her ideas freely and has a lack of fluency in her speaking skill due to self-doubt, anxiety and character despite the fact that she is teacher-instructed. For the time being, she is attending General English course. Up to now, she has already developed her writing, reading and writing skills as well as grammar competence. Yet, one of her productive language skills, that is, speaking is still her weak point.

Section 2: The role of identity

Student 1, Asya

Her L1 is Russian and she has acquired her first language subconsciously but at school, she had many Uzbek friends in a social circle. Obviously, she can speak second language as well and now she studies in a mixed group in which students mainly come from these two nationalities. This is one of the aspects, which can determine her identity. When it comes to English, she has learned this language without formal instruction by immersing herself in a communicative environment and practicing speaking with her relatives. Certainly, she has interpersonal skills and she is extrovert by nature, that's why, she can easily interact with others. The student's personality traits also build her identity. Bonny Norton (2011) states that "A great deal of language learning research in the 1970s and 1980s conceptualized the 'identities' of language learners as their fixed personalities, learning styles" (p. 419). She has a communicative competence because she mainly focuses on practicing speaking skill. But she has a lack of linguistic competence and she makes mistakes related to grammar, syntax, morphology, word formation.

In terms of social status, she has a higher position since she comes from economically advantaged family and she can enroll in for some online language courses and gain access to them. Currently, she is attending offline English course to hone her language skills and prepare for the exam. At the same time, she is teaching some young children. Therefore, she can be regarded as a teacher but her identity position changes at Lyceum since she is a student. This can has a positive impact on her performance in my classroom as a community.

As a teacher, helping her perform her identities in L2 is my responsibility. I try to create a friendly environment by giving opportunities. While doing group activities, I give the chance to control her team, check her peers' tasks, which can help her consider herself as a teacher. While accomplishing speaking, writing tasks she makes noticeable errors. Her course mates correct her and their criticism makes her feel anxious although she is self-confident. To avoid discomfort, I tend to ignore her grammar mistakes and give positive feedback. The reason why I think these actions are essential is that they can enable her to improve her identity position in classroom. The reading materials also discuss these issues. In particular, Bonny Norton states that "Even when learners possess communicative competence in an L2, they can be still be excluded by others, positioned as inadequate, unworthy or illegitimate.

To challenge this hegemonic relationship, a critical awareness of these rules of use can enable L2 speakers to deconstruct notions of legitimacy, to resist positioning themselves as inadequate or unworthy, and ultimately to claim their right to spoken environment" (p. 4). As a teacher, I have observed her and identified this problem. I intent to employ practical approaches based on my insights from reading materials.

Student 2, Guli

Guli comes from a faraway region and she had finished local school in her village before she enrolled in for the Lyceum in the city. Her first language is Uzbek. She is teacher instructed and she has been learning English for 2-3 years at a learning center. Her personality traits are shy, introvert and she feels uncomfortable in front of the class. Moreover, she has a visual learning style, she prefers to learn grammar and new words by writing a lot and she has a perfect command of writing and create texts in an accurate way. This identity certainly affects her output, that is, speaking skill and can lead to a poor performance in classroom environment. She has a lack of confidence compared to her other peers, Maybe she feels that she has a lower social status as she came to city from countryside as well as still adaptation period. That's why, she has a lack of social engagement with her peers. Norton drew on poststructuralist views and according to him, individual's identity is a site of struggle that is negotiated through language and social interaction. As a teacher, I try to help Guli overcome the adverse impact of her identity and facilitate her learning process. First off, I should pay more attention to types of tasks. Rather than written, reading assignments, focusing on output skills would be better. From my point of view, this is of paramount importance because Ramanathan (2005) advocates this view that "Language instructional practices like grammar and translation, which do not call on higher-level thinking skills, may limit language learners' progress and thus their access to more powerful identities.

This study showed how larger institutional arrangements may limit teachers' efforts to enable students to appropriate more powerful identities"(p. 431). I try to make her feel comfortable in front of her coursemates. Because she is somewhat reserved, this personality can influence her identity position in class. "In time, the learner could be positioned as a 'poor' or unmotivated language learner by others (Norton & Toohey, 2001, p. 421).

Section 3: Instructional considerations

My target students Asya and Guli are classmates, that is, they study in the same class. There are some students who know both Russian and Uzbek. Because they study in an economy group, they have more English classes compared to other groups at Lyceum. Therefore, I am responsible for conducting lessons to their group four times a week. The duration of the class is 80 minutes, which is longer than schools' lessons. As the group is divided, the number of students is 14 in my class and English classes are taught in special rooms, which are equipped with technological devices. Their group consists of students of both gender but most of them are boys and students have individual differences. The medium of instruction is Uzbek and Russian. Therefore, it is not direct method, which involves the usage of target language. Although I give more tasks related to vocabulary and translation of passages, it is not Grammar Translation Method (GTM), which is one of the most traditional methods. I try to incorporate different methods including CLT, CBI, TBI, TPR and suggestopedia in my classroom. Typically, my classes are student-centered, more students' engagement is encouraged. One of them is Communicative language teaching (CLT). Celce-Murcia, M., Dörnyei, Z., & Thurrell, S. (1995) point out that "A model of communicative competence such as ours does not directly imply anything about how teaching should proceed. However, whatever teaching approach one selects, the content must at some point undergo a "pedagogic conversion" (p. 6). The main feature of it is that content should be part of a communicative language syllabus. According to one of the existing models of communicative competence, pedagogically motivated construct includes five components.

They are: discourse competence, linguistic competence, functional competence, sociocultural competence and strategic competence. I want to entail the elements of all the instructional methods and approaches we learned during the course. I have also gained insights about Processing Instruction and principles of Input Processing (IP). According to VanPatten and Cadierno (1993), PI has three basic features. Based on these principles, I want to organize my lesson. For example, the topic is "Holidays". Firstly, learners are given information regarding a linguistic form. In other words, they are provided with the vocabulary related to the theme, which is certainly Content-based instruction (CBI) since it is related to a certain specific topic. It is considered as a pre-activity. After input, I employ IP strategy that may affect their acquiring the form or structure during the comprehension by following the component 2. What I mean is that I give instruction about some grammatical situations, which can make them confused. These are following: "At Christmas", "At Nowruz", but "On the New Year's day». These kinds of exceptional rules, instructions including not only prepositions, but also other pertinent grammar tenses, subject verb agreement are explained to students. Based on the principle 3 learners are required to process the form or structure during activities. That is, input is manipulated in different ways like games, discussion, reading and speaking materials and students are encouraged to output, by becoming dependent on form and structure. In this procedure of the lesson, I provide them with reading passage material about holidays and organize discussion for their output like Engage Study Activate ESL. After reading the passage, they accomplish the tasks including true, false, matching. It is Task based instruction (TBI) and while-activity. Based on my understanding regarding reading sources, if students cannot do intake, I may use other alternative tasks or simplify and differentiate according to the needs of students. Lastly, they are given discussion questions to consolidate what they have learned, which is a post-activity. Obviously, this activity is regarded as CLT, which is aimed at developing their communicative practice, and competence.

This can be effective for the needs of my learners; in particular, my introvert student Guli. Giving corrective feedback is also an important factor, which can affect their investment and motivation.

Section 4: Two aspects of language

Teaching Grammar

Because the age group is the same, as a teacher, my expectations for these learners are nearly the same. I chose one of the syntax topics. It is explaining “Past simple”. When it comes to teaching teenagers, I find it relatively straightforward to acquire this aspect of language. Because their level is much higher than younger learners and they have prior language experience. In addition, from a physiological point of view, their cognitive skills have developed to some extent and have a longer attention span because of their age; they can easily comprehend this grammar topic with theoretical explanation. As a language instructor, I can give teenagers detailed information about the usage of past simple, its application regarding how to use and past simple with time clauses including when, as soon as, before. That is, students can employ a critical approach towards past tenses and identify the distinction between past simple and past continuous or past perfect. Hence, my instruction must cover some other detailed aspects of past tenses instead of general explanation. I should take into account this and give suitable activities which are more complicated activities and tasks such as creating a dialogue or a small text based on the past simple topic or appropriate reading materials.

In terms of challenges depending on the age of teenagers, obviously, they typically go through a transition period, emotional and social factors have an adverse impact on them, which can impair their language learning process. They easily lose motivation towards their study because of miserable occasions, mutual disagreements with outer environment like friends or parents. Even in the worst-case scenario, they may give up learning due to teacher’s negative feedback about grammar mistakes or other bad outer effects. As a teacher, I should take into consideration this and maintain their interest during the teenage period. Another difficulty is closely associated with their confidence in speaking. Because they are learning grammar rules subconsciously, they tend to pay attention to accuracy and correctness.

If I interrupt them while speaking and correct their grammar errors, they may feel uncomfortable. It means that they may show their lack of confidence in speaking because of their anxiety. In addition, their L1 experience can affect their L2 because they usually count on their L1 knowledge. For example, Guli and Asya’s first languages are not the same, they come across differences in terms of grammar structures including subject verb agreement and other features. Therefore, their language transfer can badly influence their English learning.

In particular, Asya usually speaks English with Russian accent, stress and intonation. From a linguistic point of view, this is called “language transfer”. Gass (1996) and behaviorists of the 1950s and 1960s support this view that “language transfer as an important source of error and interference in L2 learning, because L1 'habits' were so tenacious and deeply rooted” (p. 16). As for positive sides, teenagers have long-term memory and better cognitive skills. They have developed their memory strategies and know how to remember new words or instruction in an efficient way. “The results of the comparisons indicated a significant rate advantage of the older starters, that was larger for cognitive demanding dimensions such as morph syntax, which was interpreted as resulting from the different states of cognitive maturity of older and younger learners” (Carmen Muñoz, 2006, p. 435).

Furthermore, they are almost adults and they can do self-study outside classroom environment by finding other sources from internet. They can ask for help from their other peers by sharing knowledge about this grammar topic if something is unclear for them.

Teaching morphology

I selected one of topics related to it. It is three degrees of adjective including positive, comparative and superlative forms. In terms of teenage learners, I find very simple to explain this topic. For, they have already learned these forms based on their past language experience and use in their both speaking and writing. When it comes to modification of language instruction, teenage learners ought to acquire additional morphological knowledge about types of adjectives in a detailed way. For example, they should learn one syllable ending in vowel + consonant, two syllables ending in –y. the association of the usage of superlative form with present perfect tense as well as irregular adjectives and quantifiers.

For example: pretty-prettier, big bigger (double consonant changes), far further, little least. Today was **the worst** day since I started working here is a teacher; I should pay attention to the complexity of this topic and choose appropriate teaching materials according to their level and age. As for the benefits depending on the age group, teenagers have previous L2 exposure and language experience. Therefore, they can easily understand the topic analyze and compare the distinction because of their better cognitive skills. In other words, they can consolidate their previous knowledge and develop it with their prior knowledge. As a result, they can apply adjective degrees in practice without errors by increasing their confidence. One of researchers gives his point of view about it. Salthouse (2004) notes that “Moreover, experiential factors, such as the adults' accumulated knowledge and experience, may bring advantages, like the reduction of the need for novel problem solving” (p. 440).

Section 5: Teaching philosophy statement

In my view, teaching philosophy is a broad term. Metaphorically, teachers are great gardeners who can make the souls of learner's blossom down the road and shape the future destiny of them by giving right directions. Obviously, teachers can reap the rewards of their hard work in the end, when students can demonstrate academic achievement and show worthwhile results. From a practical point of view, teaching is kind of a demanding profession. It requires much responsibility, devotion, effort and determination. This is primarily because it is essential that a teacher should take into account all aspects of learners that, is, their individual differences at the same time.

First, teachers are great problem solvers since each learner has distinctive learning strategies, approaches, styles and weak points. According to these features, teacher should tackle these kinds of situations by providing optimal, novel solutions and adapt teaching materials based on their needs. Secondly, it is important that teachers should integrate and maintain balance between inductive and deductive approaches. It means that lessons are neither student-centered nor teacher-centered. I personally agree with Kinsey's teaching philosophy. According to Kinsey (2017) “Motivation is an important affective factor for a class to be successful, so I employ various motivational strategies in my classes” (p. 7). Indeed, teachers should give motivation to students not only intellectually, but also socially. Because if a teacher encourages students on a regular basis, they try to do their best and show their full potential, which can enable them to make progress in their language journey.

From my perspective, there are rare perfect teachers in the world. Because it is difficult to find those who are proficient at their teaching career. Ideal teachers are experts in their sphere based on their theoretical knowledge. In addition, they have professional teaching pedagogical skills as well as experience. Based on the reading materials, the authors highlight

their framework on the linguists' five principles for pedagogical theory. In my opinion, two of them should be considered as crucial ones. Hawkins and Norton's (2009) state that "Second, responsiveness to learners encourages teachers to identify students' multiple identities and allow them to experiment with these. Third, dialogic engagement is the discussion of identity in the classroom" (p. 4). I agree with this view that teachers ought to be active when it comes to answering students' questions, at the same time; they should have interpersonal skills while working with students. Furthermore, knowing about students' ideologies and identities and investments can make us more effective English teachers. According to the principles, what I have also learned is that I should apply reflexivity, which involves reflection on background, education and teacher training and praxis between theory and its implementation. I have a position as a teacher's identity in the classroom, I am devoted to investing in teaching the target language to my learners and I try to give students the tasks to showcase the cultural and linguistic resources they bring to the classroom.

Personally, I consider interactive games and team working as efficient types of activities. Principle 3: Dialogic Engagement supports my view about this. According to Moll et al. (1992), "Lessons can be created with tasks that require students to actively participate and to solve problems through collaboration" (p. 11). This is primarily because students are incentivized to engage and not only do they receive information from the teacher, but also, they are given opportunity to share their own experiences as well. In addition, a higher order thinking sequence of activities suggested by Beaumont (2010) can be productive. They are aimed at developing students' critical, analytical skills.

In conclusion, teaching philosophy is a complex conception, which include a wide variety of notions related teaching language, approaches and learning process. In fact, teachers have their own teaching philosophies, interpretations, personal experience and professional backgrounds. All of them can help us to develop our pedagogy. The theories, which I learned during the SLA course, like Krashen's hypotheses and other principles, have expanded my view about teaching language and I have gained essential insights, which I can implement in my teaching career.

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